

OPTIMIZATION OF MEDICAL CARE FOR WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE IN PRIMARY CARE

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Abstract. This article talks about the health reforms implemented in our country to strengthen the reproductive health of the population, protect motherhood and childhood, give birth to a healthy child, and raise a physically and spiritually mature generation. The practical work carried out in our country to protect the health of mothers and children was recognized by the deputies. Protection of mothers and children is a system of state and social-medical activities aimed at maintaining and strengthening the health of mothers and children, raising healthy, physically and mentally competent children.

Keywords: maternal and child health, healthy childbirth, reproductive health care, new universal progressive, screening.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассказывается о медико-санитарных реформах, проводимых в нашей стране для укрепления репродуктивного здоровья населения, охраны материнства и детства, рождения здорового ребенка, воспитания физически и духовно зрелого поколения. Практическая работа, проводимая в нашей стране по охране здоровья матери и ребенка, получила признание депутатов. Охрана материнства и детства – это система государственной и социально-медицинской деятельности, направленная на сохранение и укрепление здоровья матери и ребенка, воспитание здоровых, физически и умственно компетентных детей.

Ключевые слова: здоровье матери и ребенка, здоровые роды, охрана репродуктивного здоровья, новый универсальный прогрессивный скрининг.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada mamlakatimizda aholining reproduktiv salomatligini mustahkamlash, onalik va bolalikni muhofaza qilish, sog'lom farzandni dunyoga keltirish, jismonan va ma'nan yetuk avlodni tarbiyalash borasida amalga oshirilayotgan sog'liqni saqlash sohasida amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlar haqida so'z boradi. Mamlakatimizda onalar va bolalar salomatligini muhofaza qilish borasida amalga oshirilayotgan amaliy ishlar deputatlar e'tirofiga sazovor bo'ldi. Ona va bola salomatligini muhofaza qilish - onalar va bolalar salomatligini saqlash va mustahkamlash, sog'lom, jismonan va aqlan barkamol bolalarni tarbiyalashga qaratilgan davlat va ijtimoiy-tibbiy faoliyat tizimi muhimdir.

Kalit so'zlar: ona va bola salomatligi, sog'lom tug'ilish, reproduktiv salomatlik, yangi universal progressiv skrining.

Relevance. In recent years, a number of laws, presidential decrees and decisions have been adopted aimed at expanding the access to quality medical services for mothers and children, providing them with specialized and high-tech medical care, maintaining reproductive health, and preventing the death of infants and children. In this direction, perinatal, screening, reproductive health and diagnostic centers, maternity wards, multidisciplinary polyclinic, family polyclinic and rural medical centers are providing medical services to the population in all regions of the republic. The practical work carried out in our country to protect the health of mothers and children was recognized by the deputies. Protection of mothers and children is a system of state and social-medical activities aimed at maintaining and strengthening the health of mothers and children, raising healthy, physically and mentally competent children. In the

Republic of Uzbekistan, this system is based on the creation of networks of special treatment and prevention institutions that provide labor protection for women, pregnant women and nursing mothers, socio-legal protection of mothers and children, as well as obstetrics-gynecology and pediatrics. After the country gained independence, programs were developed with comprehensive measures aimed at mothers and children. Since 1998, the scientific-practical center "Family" has been operating in Tashkent; in this center, scientific research works are carried out on the problems of family formation and demographic development in Uzbekistan. Working hours of mothers with young children are limited by the state, they are given the opportunity to work part-time, part-time week, as well as at their own convenience or at home, depending on the need.

It is the responsibility of the state to monitor the health of every mother and child and provide them with qualified medical care. In order to raise a healthy generation, various networks such as preschool education, school, boarding school, children's health complexes are being developed by state bodies, organizations and institutions. In particular, in order to improve the health of women and teenage girls and improve the reproductive health of expectant mothers, to improve the quality of medical care for pregnant women, to strengthen the health of mothers, "Women's consultation rooms" and departments of girls' health are organized in primary medical and sanitary institutions. The measures taken to cover the population with preventive examinations, systematic patronage and strengthening of reproductive health are bearing results.

Every 2 minutes, one woman in the world dies due to cervical cancer. According to the World Health Organization, more than 600,000 cases are reported worldwide each year. Despite the measures taken, 50% of women die from this disease. According to (2000), cervical cancer ranks fifth among all oncological diseases in Uzbekistan and accounts for 13%. In Uzbekistan, it is the second most common type of cancer in the reproductive organs after breast cancer. Since 2000, the disease has been increasing in Uzbekistan. According to the OITI of the UzR, in 2008, the intensive rate of this disease was 4.2 per 100,000 population.

At the beginning of the 70s of the last century, a hypothesis was put forward about the role of viruses in the origin of cervical tumor diseases, after some time this hypothesis was proven. Epidemiological and experimental studies conducted in the last 10 years have proved that there is a correlation between genital infection and human papillomavirus in cervical neoplasia (CIN). In 1996, the information bulletin of the World Health Organization officially confirmed that the cause of cervical cancer is the Papilloma Virus. There is a direct relationship between cervical cancer, HPV infection (Papilloma virus) and genital herpes. For example: Human papilloma virus (HPV) affects 95% of women with cervical cancer. If a woman is at risk of infection with both types of virus, the number of infections is 3 times higher than in a healthy person.

The purpose of the study. To study the role of nurses in the use of the clinical visual method in the diagnosis of cervical diseases.

Materials and methods. To achieve this goal, 200 women were treated with 3-5% acetic acid and Lugol's solution using a clinical visual method, and women with changes were sent for colposcopy to confirm the diagnosis. The obtained results were analyzed statistically.

Obtained results and discussion. Women of childbearing age living in this area were examined during the "Health Week". 200 of them were examined using the clinical visual method. Women's age ranged from 17 to 63 years (table), married women made up 83%, and those without families made up 17%.

A survey was conducted on the basis of questionnaires prepared to determine the cases of possible damage to the cervix of women. In this questionnaire, the following questions were asked: at what age they started sexual life, the number of sexual partners, the number of births, the number of abortions, the presence of gynecological diseases, etc. The majority of women - 45% started their sexual life at the age of 17-20, 25% at the age of 21-26 and 30% got married before the age of 35.

According to their answers, most of the women who participated in our study were diagnosed with gynecological diseases, 72% were diagnosed with erosion of the cervix, 15% with cervicitis, 7% with uterine fibroids, and 6% with other types of diseases. During childbirth, 125 women (62.5%) had cervical tear. After taking a complete medical history from the women, a vaginal speculum was poured into the cervix and the cervix was examined. This helped us to determine whether a woman has cervical diseases - erosion, polyp, endocervicitis and background diseases. After that, the cervix of all women was treated with 3-5% acetic acid by clinical visual method, after 3 minutes the changes observed in the cervix were recorded in the journal. At the next stage, "Schiller's test" was poured with Lugol's solution. After that, women with a positive test result were divided into separate groups. Out of 200 women under our observation, 33 (16.5%) had a positive test result. These women were sent to the "Center for Population and Reproductive Health of the Republic" for a more in-depth examination for a colposcopic examination and special tests for cervical diseases. Out of 33 women, 13 had endocervicitis (43%), 8 had cervical erosion (24%), 4 had adnexitis (13%), 3 had uterine fibroids (9%), and the same number had colpitis (9%), one woman had cervical myoma (3%) and only 1 woman (3%) was found to be absolutely healthy. It should be noted that the women had absolutely no knowledge of the diseases detected in this examination, and they did not notice any symptoms of this disease. Therefore, conducting a screening examination among women helps to detect the disease in the early stages, get it under medical supervision, and increases the effectiveness of the treatment. In September 2010, a 2-day scientific and practical seminar on "The importance of clinical-visual methods in the prevention of cervical cancer" was organized together with the Tashkent City Health Department and the "Eastern Woman" International Foundation. The participants of the seminar were chief nurses of family polyclinics of Tashkent city. On the first day of the seminar, in order to evaluate the knowledge and skills of nurses, test questions were held. Test questions were devoted to cervical diseases, etiology, early diagnosis, and prevention.

Healthcare professionals attended a national level meeting in Tashkent to learn about the new universal progressive model of patronage service. The heads of regional health departments of the Ministry, chief nurses of all regions, as well as representatives of scientific circles got acquainted with the guidelines on practical recommendations for identifying risk factors in mothers and children, and received advice, a new model of patronage service in the primary system learned how to implement. "The new model of patronage service focuses not only on identifying diseases and medical problems, but also on quality implementation of a set of medical-social, educational and other health activities." Newborn care is a compulsory health program provided free of charge in the community. The pediatrician who comes to the house examines the newborn, examines the condition of the mother and gives the necessary recommendations for child care. In addition, the duties of the patronage nurse include checking the living conditions of the family and the compliance of the baby's place of residence with all the established norms and requirements. The first visit of the pediatrician is made within three days after the newborn and the mother are discharged from the hospital. After that, the patronage

nurse will come to the house several more times during the month. If the parents do not want to conduct such observation, they should write a written application, indicating the objective reason for the refusal. The patronage nurse is a person who comes to your home and a qualified medical professional who provides assistance in the care of a newborn baby (in patronage of a newborn baby) and performs routine medical procedures. The patronage nurse monitors not only the condition of the ward, but also the living conditions. Also, his tasks include timely notification to the attending physician about changes in the patient's health, monitoring the availability and reception of all necessary medications, providing psychological support to the patient and caring for his relatives. includes teaching the necessary procedures for doing things. It can be sent from your local hospital, paid patronage service, charity non-profit organization.

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Conclusions. Screening among women led to early detection of cervical diseases (16.5%). Increasing knowledge and skills of cervical diseases, prevention, and early diagnosis can lead to detection of the disease in the early stages, improvement of preventive measures, and effective use of doctors' time. Training of midwives and nurses in the clinical-visual method will further increase their knowledge about cervical diseases and will lead to the widespread use of this method and the detection of the disease in the primary joint. Mother and child care includes the organization of 2 main departments: obstetrics-gynecology (giving birth) and treatment-prophylactic care for children. Obstetrics and gynecology care is provided by special institutions, in particular, maternity hospitals in the city, as well as hospital complexes with women's consultation rooms, obstetrics and gynecology departments of hospitals, scientific research institutes of obstetrics and gynecology, departments of this field within the department of obstetrics and gynecology of medical institutions, women's consultation rooms, polyclinics and Obstetrics-gynecology offices under the medical-sanitary department of production enterprises carry out. Obstetrics and gynecology assistance to women in rural areas is provided by maternity wards of regional and district hospitals, outpatient clinics, paramedics and obstetrics and gynecology offices in polyclinics.

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